

ABSORPTION AND FLUORESCENCE SPECTRA OF FLAVONES

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Absorption and fluorescence spectra of 4'-methoxyflavones with methyl and benzoyl substitutions and 4'-benzyloxyflavones with methyl and methoxy substitutions are reported and discussed.

Additional resonance due to a 4'-methoxy group in flavones results in a red-shift of the flavone spectrum. Introduction of methyl groups produces a slight bathochromic effect. Benzoyl substitution in 6-position increases conjugation to a large extent, and the possibility of additional resonance causes a radical change in the spectrum. The behaviour of 4'-benzyloxy substitution is not very much different from a 4'-methoxy, except in the high-frequency region.

Introduction of methyl groups or replacement of 4'-methoxy by 4'-benzyloxy increases the fluorescence efficiency slightly. 6-Benzoyl group shifts the fluorescence maximum to red and causes a sharp fall in efficiency. A very large increase in efficiency by the introduction of 6-Me, 3'-OMe or 7:3'-dimethoxy groups in 4'-benzyloxyflavone is observed.

A solvent effect in the fluorescence of flavones (not 3-OH derivatives, i.e. flavonols) has been observed in as much as the quantum efficiency increases considerably when the proportion of water in the EtOH-water solvent pair is increased. The effect is observable by qualitative methods and may prove of importance in identification of flavones (flavonols and isomeric benzylidene-commaranones do not behave in this manner).

Earlier work on the absorption spectra of flavones is that of the Japanese workers (Shibata, *Acta Phytochim.*, 1922, 1, 95; Hattori, *ibid.*, 1932, 6, 131; Hayashi, *ibid.*, 1935, 8, 179; 1936, 9, 1) who have shown that this series is characterised by two bands at 2,500 and 3,000 Å. Skarzyn'ski (*Biochem. Z.*, 1939, 301, 150) studied the absorption spectra of a number of flavones in the light of their chemical constitution. According to him, the absorption of flavones depends on the presence of benzopyrone.

Aronoff (*J. Org. Chem.*, 1940, 8, 561) showed that neither the phenyl group of flavone, as supposed by Shibata (*loc. cit.*), nor the benzo- γ -pyrone, as supposed by Skarzyn'ski (*loc. cit.*) was responsible for the flavone spectra. According to him, an oxygen in the phenone is involved which is capable of *ortho-para* resonance. Owing to restriction of the normal resonance of the pyrilium nucleus by a ketonic oxygen, the additional resonances caused by substitution follow a path through this oxygen, resulting in a shift of one band of the spectrum to the red (e.g., 4', 7-, 2'-OH substitutions).

Other work on absorption spectra of flavones includes such data for a number of polyhydroxy flavones and their methyl ethers, mostly naturally occurring substances (cf. Marchlewski and Skarzyn'ski, *Biochem. Z.*, 1938, 297, 56; Briggs and Locker, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 2157; 1951, 3131). Mansfield *et al.* (*Nature*, 1953, 172, 23) have utilised the ultraviolet spectra of the ions of hydroxyflavones as a means of their identification.

Study of fluorescence spectra of flavones has not been so far reported. Qualitative study of the exhibition of fluorescence in relation to chemical constitution has been made by Seshadri and his co-workers (*Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1940, 12A, 375; 1951, 34A, 319).

Their study includes visual examination of the fluorescence, excited by daylight. No regard was taken of the exciting radiation, nor the concentration at which the solutions were viewed. As in chromones, these authors found concentrated H_2SO_4 as the medium in which flavones exhibited visible fluorescence. Pyrone double bond is found essential for fluorescence; flavanones do not fluoresce.

In the present work the absorption and fluorescence spectra of flavones have been discussed; the data are shown in Figs. 1-4.

Absorption

The substitution in 4'-position in flavone by an OH group causes a bathochromic shift of the long-wave band. According to Aronoff (*loc. cit.*) this is due to the following additional resonance:

As similar resonance is possible with 4'- OCH_3 - and 4'- $OCH_2\phi$ -flavones, we have observed a similar shift towards the red.

4'-Methoxyflavone has a broad and intense band at $317 m\mu$ (oscillator strength 0.605) with $\epsilon=24,100$, and two other bands at $253.5 m\mu$ and $221 m\mu$ with $\epsilon=12,500$ and $19,670$ respectively. The spectra of 4'-methoxyflavone (and its Me derivatives) in neutral, $10^{-4}N$ alkaline and $10^{-4}N$ acidic media show no remarkable variation, especially in the longest wave-band, but there is a slight decrease in absorption in acid and alkaline media, which is more prominent in the $253 m\mu$ band. This is now obviously not due to any ionisation, but, as found by Gibbs (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 52, 4895) too, there is a tendency to form pyronium salts.

Methyl groups in 6- and 8- positions of 4'-methoxyflavone produce a slight bathochromic shift, perhaps hyperconjugative in character. The integrated absorption also increases on introduction of these methyl groups. The oscillator strengths of the $320m\mu$ bands of 6- and 8- methyl derivatives are 0.62 and 0.61 as compared to 0.605, when there is no alkyl substitution.

Introduction of a benzoyl group at 6- position, which basically changes the character of the resonance, produces radical changes in absorption (see Fig. 3).

The integrated absorption, $\int \epsilon d\nu$, for 6-benzoyl derivative is 112.0 as compared to 74.5, when this substitution is absent.

FIG. 2

FIG. 1

FIG. 4

FIG. 3

Except for minor changes, the replacement of a $-OCH_3$ by $-OCH_2\phi$ does not change the nature of spectrum. However, the phenyl group does contribute to the total absorption as $-O-CH_2-\phi$ is incapable of complete insulation from the rest of the molecule.

6-Me-3'- OCH_3 substitution in 4'-benzyloxyflavone causes a bathochromic shift ($\Delta\lambda = 10.5 m\mu$) in the longest wave-band, and an increase in $\int \epsilon d\nu$ (from 86.0 to 93.0), but retains the nature of the spectrum, because $-OCH_3$ in 3'-position cannot produce any additional resonance, as it does when in *para* (4'-) or *ortho* (2'-) position.

7:3'-Dimethoxy substitution, however, makes a difference; 7- OCH_3 group can give rise to the resonance of the type:

Now there appears an additional (unresolved) band indicated by a shoulder at $305m\mu$ in addition to maxima at 336 and $237.5m\mu$. The appearance of an intense short-wave band at $212m\mu$ is also a deviation from the other two benzyloxyflavones described above. $\int \epsilon d\nu$ now increases to 108.3.

Fluorescence

The fact that simple flavone fluoresces shows that a free hydroxyl is, unlike chromones, not necessary to make the compound exhibit fluorescence. The 2-phenyl substitution in chromone nucleus increases resonance, so much so that even without a hydroxyl in a favourable position, the flavones are fluorescent.

4'-Methoxyflavone is found to exhibit a blue-violet emission excited by hydrogen discharge. The fluorescence band has maximum at $425m\mu$ and extends roughly from $380m\mu$ to $520m\mu$. Methyl substitution at 6- or 8- position does not make any significant difference. Thus, 6- and 8- methyl derivatives have λ_{max}^F at 425 and $423m\mu$ respectively and relative $\int Fd\nu$ equal to 1170 and 900 respectively, as compared to relative $\int Fd\nu$ of 960 for 4'-methoxyflavone. The higher total fluorescence of 6-methyl derivative does not indicate a higher yield because of its correspondingly higher integrated absorption; it has roughly the same efficiency as that of 4'-methoxyflavone.

Replacement of 4'- OCH_3 by 4'-benzyloxy makes only a slight increase ($\sim 20\%$) in efficiency, while the λ_{max}^F of the fluorescence band does not shift. Introduction of 6-methyl, 3'-methoxy or 7:3'-dimethoxy groups in 4'-benzyloxyflavone, however, makes a great difference, in as much as the efficiency increases considerably (roughly 7-8 times), and also a shift in λ_{max}^F to $465m\mu$ and $445m\mu$ respectively. There is a red-shift of the longest-wave absorption band on introduction of these groups which may partly be responsible for a similar effect in fluorescence spectrum. The effect of 7:3'-dimethoxy

substitution can be expected because of the increase in resonance due to 7-OCH₃, but that of 6-Me-3'-OCH₃ substitution, which is as significant as the former, is not clear at present.

Introduction of a benzoyl group in 6-position of 4'-methoxyflavone causes a sharp fall in efficiency ($f_{\text{rel}}^{\text{em}}$ and relative $f_{\text{rel}}^{\text{ab}}$ for 4'-methoxyflavone and its 6-benzoyl derivative being 74.5; 960 and 112.0; 170 respectively). A red-shift in absorption is also apparent in the fluorescence spectrum ($\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{f}}$ now being at 440m μ). The decrease in efficiency is possibly due to hampering of the normal electron drift from anionoid oxygen at 1 to cationoid oxygen at 4-position. The 'inner-filter' effect due to higher absorption in the blue region will also account for a slight fall in efficiency.

A solvent effect, which may be of importance in identification of flavones, is found to be characteristic of flavone derivatives and absent (or much less so as to escape observation by qualitative methods) in flavonols and other compounds isomeric with flavones, e.g. benzylidene-coumaranones. When an alcoholic solution (exhibiting no fluorescence in daylight) is largely diluted with water, a distinct violet fluorescence is given rise to. It was found to be common to all the flavones studied here (except, of course, 6-benzoyl derivative). Quantitative measurements for 4'-methoxyflavone showed that the F_{max} as well as $f_{\text{rel}}^{\text{ab}}$ increased almost linearly with increase in the proportion of water in EtOH-water solvent pair (Table I).

TABLE I

% Water	...	4	28	52	75
$\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{f}}$ (m μ)	...	425	425	430	432
F_{max}	...	585	2,050	3,395	4,455
$f_{\text{rel}}^{\text{ab}}$	...	960	3,625	6,510	10,025

There is, however, no significant change in absorption spectrum when changing the proportion of water in the solvent. Why the higher dielectric constant of water causes a large increase in quantum efficiency of the emission in case of flavones and not flavonols or other isomers should make an interesting study. The slight red-shift in fluorescence maximum with higher dielectric constant of the solvent is in conformity with the results reported by previous workers (cf. Ganguly, *Science & Culture*, 1946, 12, 114).

EXPERIMENTAL

Measurements of the ultraviolet absorption spectra and fluorescence spectra were made in the manner as described in a previous paper (this *Journal*, 1956, 33, 604). Measurements of absorption were made at a concentration of $1.5 \times 10^{-4}M$ in neutral, $10^{-4}N$ -HCl and $10^{-4}N$ -KOH media. The solvent was aqueous alcohol (87%). Fluorescence spectra were taken in alcoholic (96%) solution at the same molar concentration. Alcohol was purified according to Harris (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 55, 1940) and Clow and Pearson (*Nature*, 1939, 144, 208). 1 cm (± 0.001 cm) cells were used for

taking absorption spectra; the readings were taken at $10\text{\AA}$ intervals at maxima and minima and these were located to $5\text{\AA}$, whenever possible. The accuracy in ϵ_{max} values is within $\pm 1\%$ and $\bar{\nu}_{\text{max}}$ values are correct to $\pm 0.2\%$. The errors in $\bar{\nu}$ values of ϵ_{max} due to the different fluorescing capacities of the various compounds studied are intrinsic in these measurements.

Integrated absorption (between the limits $2,100\text{\AA}$ and $5,000\text{\AA}$) and fluorescence have been calculated from the areas of the respective spectral curves, measured planimetrically. In comparing fluorescence efficiencies qualitatively, no cognizance has been taken of the spectral distribution in the exciting radiation. One is not-unjustified in doing so, as long as the absorption spectra are very similar in nature. The compounds used were pure as judged by their m.p.'s.

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